

Random Fiber-Matrix Model for Predicting Damage in Multiscale Analysis of Textile Composites under Thermomechanical Loads

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1 Introduction

Failure prediction in structures containing carbon fiber polymer matrix composites is complicated by the various scales at which damage and failure can occur. In order to understand and predict how a composite structure will fail under a complex thermomechanical load, a variety of mechanisms at different scales must be taken into account. At the microscale, where fibers and matrix are modeled as discrete constituents, temperature changes induce stresses due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the constituents. Interactions between these thermally-induced stresses and stresses from mechanical loading change the apparent strength of tows or laminas when observed at larger scales. Failure at the microscale is further complicated by the inherent randomness that characterizes the arrangement of individual fibers. This leads to enhanced stress concentrations where fibers are in very close proximity to one another. These stress concentrations will have a significant effect on extreme-driven phenomena such as failure.

At the intermediate scale (often referred to as the meso-scale) in which the fibers and matrix are homogenized, but individual tows (or lamina, in the case of tapes) are modeled discretely, thermal loads can further influence whether a given mechanical load will cause failure. This is due to thermally-induced stresses that arise from the thermal expansion mismatch between the different tows and the neat matrix pocket.

Several previous studies have focused on failure at the microscale with the goal of characterizing failure at larger scales in the composite [1–3]. Recently, there have been a number of investigations into

microscale failure utilizing random microstructures [4–6]. The current work builds on these investigations by using a model of the random fiber-matrix microscale to investigate how thermally-induced stresses change the apparent strength of tows.

Failure investigations at the scale of textile unit cells have also been conducted for some time [7–9]. Recent work has introduced methods for discretely accounting for matrix cracking in the tows of a plain-weave composite under a variety of multiaxial loadings using a cohesive zone model [10]. The current work incorporates information regarding the uncertainty and thermal dependence of failure at the fiber-matrix microscale into this larger-scale analysis.

The primary goal of this work is to demonstrate an approach for integrating models at these two scales. A description of the configuration at each scale is given along with the methods used to communicate data from the microscale to the textile scale. The progressive failure models are described as well as the material properties utilized in the analyses. Several issues are then investigated using the microscale model. The first is determining the effect of RVE size on failure predictions. The second major issue is the determination of microscale strength parameters that cause the fiber-matrix model to predict tow strengths for the composite that match experiments for unidirectional tape laminates. It is assumed that the strength of an individual tow and a unidirectional tape are comparable. For a given realization of the random microstructure, the “tow strength” is defined to be the maximum volume-averaged stress attained by the fiber-matrix

model as it undergoes damage. An inverse approach is utilized to identify the appropriate microscale strengths. This study also includes an investigation into the effect of different approaches for degrading failed material. Once appropriate microscale strength parameters are identified, the fiber-matrix model is utilized to characterize the dependence of the tow strength on changes in thermally induced stress. Information from these investigations of the fiber-matrix microscale is then applied to a progressive failure analysis of a textile unit cell.

2 Multi-scale Modeling Approach

Fig. 1 illustrates the way that data flows between the different scales. The local stress and strain fields in the textile unit cell correspond to the volume-averaged stress and strain in the fiber-matrix microscale. Linear analyses at the microscale yield the elastic moduli of tows. Progressive failure analysis of the fiber-matrix microscale is utilized to predict the stresses at which a tow will fail. This analysis includes a thermally-induced stress field to capture its effect on tow failure. The microstructure is generated through a method described in [11]. The resulting microstructural realizations possess the following salient characteristics:

- Randomly positioned fibers
- Fibers in very close proximity to one another, which leads to large stress concentrations
- Periodicity in the geometry and mesh, which simplifies the application of periodic boundary conditions described in [12]

The presence of randomness in the microstructure requires an ensemble of progressive failure simulations to be run. Each simulation in the ensemble is for a different realization of the microstructure. This yields a collection of tow strength values that are fit with a Weibull distribution. The probability density function for a Weibull distribution is given by

$$f(x) \begin{cases} \frac{k}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} e^{-(x/\lambda)^k} & x \geq 0 \\ 0 & x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where k is the scale parameter and λ is the shape parameter. The computational cost of simulating

each realization is reduced by exploiting the quasi-3D nature of the displacement field to reduce the analysis to a two-dimensional domain as described by Pipes and Pagano [13].

Once strength distributions have been characterized using the fiber-matrix model, they can be used to predict matrix failure of the composite material at larger scales where the fibers and matrix are homogenized, such as the tows in a textile unit-cell model. The current investigation is for a plain-weave textile composite with a waviness ratio of 1/9. Waviness ratio WR is related to the unit cell dimensions shown in Fig. 1 by

$$WR = \frac{t}{w} \quad (2)$$

This textile unit cell has been utilized in a variety of previous studies [8], [14], [15]. Transverse strength values for the tows are seeded at quadrature points using the tow strength distribution from the fiber-matrix model. In this way, both strength variability due to the randomness of the fiber positions and the effect of thermally-induced stresses at the fiber-matrix scale are incorporated into the textile-scale analysis. The methods investigated here are also applicable to tape laminates.

3 Progressive Failure Modeling

This section describes the methods utilized to model progressive failure in both the fiber-matrix model and the textile unit cell. The microscale fiber-matrix model utilizes a quadrature point degradation approach applied to the matrix. Fiber failure is not considered. This simple damage model was deemed appropriate for these early investigations into the behavior of this fiber-matrix model. Damage in the textile unit cell is modeled using cohesive zones.

3.1 Christensen Failure Criterion

Damage in the fiber-matrix model is accounted for by degrading elastic properties at quadrature points in the matrix that undergo failure. The isotropic failure criterion of Christensen [16] is used to predict when local failure occurs in the matrix. This two-part criterion is given by

$$\sigma_{kk} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{C} \right) + \frac{\sigma_{VM}^2}{CT} = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_I = T \quad \text{if } T \leq \frac{C}{2} \quad (4)$$

T and C are the tensile and compressive material strengths, σ_{kk} is the trace of the stress tensor, σ_{VM} is the von Mises stress, and σ_I is the largest tensile principle stress. The second criterion only applies for values of T and C which satisfy the inequality in Eq. (4). According to Christensen, failure predicted by the criterion of Eq. (4) will always be brittle in nature. The criterion in Eq. (3), however, can indicate brittle or ductile failure depending on the magnitude of the hydrostatic stress according to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3} < T - \frac{C}{3} & \quad \text{Ductile} \\ \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3} > T - \frac{C}{3} & \quad \text{Brittle} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Essentially, failure under strongly hydrostatic stress tends to be brittle while failure under strongly deviatoric stress tends to be ductile.

Two different property degradation models are examined in the current study. The first disregards the brittle or ductile nature of failure and scales the stiffness of any failed quadrature point by a factor of 1e-6, essentially deleting it. The second approach that is utilized scales the stiffness at each quadrature point in the matrix by a factor (1.0-d), where d is a damage parameter that starts with an initial value of zero and increases monotonically to one. For brittle failure $d = 1.0 \cdot 1e-6$ (which results in the same stiffness drop as the first degradation method). However, for ductile failure, d is increased by a value of 0.001 each time the failure criterion is exceeded at a quadrature point. This modification to the degradation should better reproduce the gradual redistribution of stress that occurs around a location which undergoes ductile failure.

3.2 Cohesive Zone Formulation

In the textile unit cell, damage is accounted for through the use of interfacial elements with opening governed by the cohesive zone formulation of Turon et al. [17]. The reader is referred to that work for a full description of this formulation.

The traction-separation behavior of the cohesive interface is governed by a bilinear traction-

separation law illustrated in Fig. 2. In equation form, this traction-separation law takes the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tau_n \\ \tau_{t_1} \\ \tau_{t_2} \end{Bmatrix} = (1-d) K_p \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta_n \\ \Delta_{t_1} \\ \Delta_{t_2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

τ is the traction and Δ is the opening displacement. K_p is a large penalty stiffness that resists crack opening before failure. d is a damage parameter that increases monotonically from zero to one as the cohesive zone opens. The subscripts n , t_1 , and t_2 indicate the normal and two tangential directions relative to the interface.

As the opening increases, the damage parameter d is related to Δ^{eff} (the Euclidean norm of the opening displacement), Δ^0 (the effective opening at which softening starts), and Δ^f (the effective opening at which the interfacial traction goes to zero) through the following relationship

$$d = \frac{\Delta^f (\Delta^{eff} - \Delta^0)}{\Delta^{eff} (\Delta^f - \Delta^0)} \quad (7)$$

The evolution of the damage parameter d is irreversible throughout the entire analysis. If Δ^{eff} decreases at some stage of an analysis, d remains constant until Δ^{eff} increases again beyond its previous maximum level

In order to facilitate incorporation of this formulation into the current progressive failure algorithm, one significant modification has been made to the formulation put forward by Turon et al. In the current implementation, the effective opening Δ^{eff} used to calculate d is only permitted to attain one of 50 equally-spaced values ranging from Δ^0 to Δ^f . Without this modification, the damage iteration portion of the progressive failure algorithm takes an exceedingly large number of iterations to converge due to the fact that each iteration can result in an arbitrarily small increase in damage and degradation of the cohesive interface. Investigations have shown that this modification introduces negligible error into the analysis.

Interface elements are inserted into the textile unit cell mesh along likely crack paths. Fig. 3 gives some detail of the textile unit cell mesh, and Fig. 4 shows the locations in the y-direction tow where

cohesive zones are inserted. Additional cohesive zones are located in the x-direction tows, neat matrix pockets, and on all material interfaces.

3.3 Progressive Failure Executive

Both the micromechanics and textile unit cell progressive failure models are implemented using the following progressive failure procedure:

- 1) Increment the load
- 2) Perform damage iterations for current load
 - a) Solve for the equilibrium displacements using the current damage state
 - b) Examine the stress state at each matrix or cohesive zone quadrature point and increase the degradation if necessary
 - c) If degradation increased for any quadrature point, return to step 2a
 - d) If there was no increase in degradation for any quadrature point, output data for the loadstep and exit the iterative loop (go to step 3)
- 3) If the maximum load has been exceeded or this load step resulted in a 20% or greater drop in the model's effective stiffness, stop the analysis. Otherwise, return to step 1

4 Material Properties

Material properties are the means by which the two scales are linked. The following sections describe the properties utilized in both the fiber-matrix and textile unit cell models. Elastic properties are provided along with the cohesive zone parameters.

4.1 Elastic Properties

The material system being investigated consists of IM7 fibers and 8552 epoxy matrix. The elastic material properties for the constituents are given in Table 1. The matrix properties are those for neat 8552. The transversely isotropic fiber properties were obtained through an inverse problem using the currently described fiber-matrix microstructure. Fiber properties were identified which caused the microscale model to predict elastic properties that matched IM7/8552 lamina properties given by Jumbo et al. [18]. The thermal expansion coefficients for the fibers were found experimentally by Kulkarni and Ochoa [19].

Elastic properties for tows with $V_f=60\%$ were obtained using the fiber-matrix model and are given in table 2. The properties for the neat matrix pockets in the textile unit cell are the same as those used in the fiber-matrix model.

4.2 Cohesive Zone Properties

The following material properties are needed for the cohesive interfaces:

- G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} : Critical strain energy release rate under mode I and mode II type openings
- η : A shape parameter defining G_c under mixed mode opening
- τ_n^0 and τ_t^0 : The normal and tangential cohesive strengths
- K_p : Penalty stiffness, which is specified to $2e15$ Pa/m for all materials

The properties used for the cohesive zones in the current study are given in table 3. Many of these values are not specified in the literature, requiring a number of assumptions to be made where noted. A discussion of these assumptions is provided in [10]. As noted in table 3, the cohesive strengths for the intra-tow cohesive zones come from the fiber-matrix model. These cohesive strengths correspond to transverse tensile and shear strength of the tow. Therefore, they are determined from the Weibull strength distributions which are obtained using the fiber-matrix microscale analysis. At the beginning of the textile analysis, cohesive strength values are seeded at the quadrature points for the intra-tow cohesive zones using these distributions.

5 Results

The following sections describe the results of investigations performed using the progressive failure models of the fiber-matrix RVEs and the textile unit cell.

5.1 Microscale Behavior

First, the effect of RVE size on the apparent strength of the fiber-matrix was investigated to determine an appropriate RVE size. Then, the inverse problem of determining apparent matrix strengths was undertaken. Finally, these strengths were used to study how the tow strength distribution is affected

by changes in the thermally-induced stress. The following subsections describe these investigations.

5.1.1 Dependence on RVE Size

One of the challenges associated with performing failure analysis on a random microstructure is the issue of RVE size dependence. Because failure is an extreme-driven phenomenon, it is expected that for a given RVE size, the predicted tow strength will exhibit greater scatter than properties such as effective elastic moduli. Therefore, a study was undertaken to determine how the tow strength distribution changes as the RVE size is increased. This study examined failure under transverse tensile loading using the quadrature point deletion degradation model.

To accomplish this study, T and C were assigned values of 150 MPa, which is within the range of the strengths observed for tests on neat epoxy resins. Subsequent investigations showed that the nature of the tow strength dependence on RVE size was unchanged for significantly different values of T and C . Progressive failure analyses were performed for RVEs containing from 25 to 800 fibers. For each RVE size, at least 200 realizations were run and a Weibull distribution was fit to the resulting tow strengths. The probability density functions of these distributions are compared to one another in Fig. 5. Several trends were noted in the strength distribution as the RVE size increased. The first was a decrease in the width of the distribution – as the RVE size increases, the predicted tow strength becomes more certain. The second trend that was noted was a downward shift in the strength distribution as RVE size increases. However, the lower-end of the distributions appeared to be fairly consistent for all RVE sizes. This characteristic suggests that there are features which can exist in the microstructure that tend to decrease an RVE's strength. As RVE size increases, the likelihood of such a feature existing in a given realization increases. This has the effect of driving the average strength downwards towards a “minimum” strength value as the RVE size is increased.

Assuming that the observed trend continues, a very large RVE would have a strength that is near the lower end of the strength distribution obtained from

smaller RVE sizes. Therefore, if one is attempting to develop a progressive failure micromechanics model based on strength data from experiments (which are performed on specimens which are essentially very large RVEs), the experimental strength value should match the lower end of the tow strength distributions from smaller RVE sizes.

Based on these findings and due to computational constraints, it was decided to utilize an RVE size of 100 fibers for the subsequent studies into behavior at the scale of the fibers and matrix.

5.1.2 In-Situ Matrix Strength

The next aspect of the fiber-matrix model that was investigated was the determination of matrix strengths T and C . The goal was to determine matrix strengths that cause the fiber-matrix model to predict tow strengths that match experiments. The experimental values used were lamina strengths under transverse tension and in-plane shear loading. The fiber-matrix model consisted of a collection of over 200 realizations of RVEs containing 100 fibers each. Based on the findings of the RVE size study, it was decided to match the 5th percentile of the strength distribution from the fiber-matrix model (i.e. the value that is greater than 5% and smaller than 95% of the realizations' strengths) to the experimental strength for both loadings.

For IM7/8552, the experimental strengths are 60 MPa for transverse tensile loading and 90 MPa for in-plane shear loading [18]. A temperature change of $\Delta T = -160$ °C was applied to the microstructure to account for the thermal stresses resulting from post-cure cooling [20].

The matrix strength values were determined through an iterative linear root-finding procedure. The 5th percentile tow strengths were obtained for transverse tensile loading and in-plane shear using three different sets of values for the matrix strengths T and C . A new estimate for T and C was then made using linear interpolation based on the errors in the 5th percentile tow strengths. This new estimate for T and C yielded tow strengths that were much closer to the experimental values. This process was repeated until the 5th percentile tow strengths were within one MPa of the experimental values.

Several iterations of this process yielded matrix strength values of $T=239$ MPa and $C=2601$ MPa for the quadrature-point deletion degradation approach. The histograms and probability density functions for the tow strengths are given in Fig. 6. These matrix strength values, particularly the compressive strength, are unreasonably large for a polymer. It was noted that matching the tow shear strength to experimental values was the primary reason for the large value of C . If only transverse tension were considered, lower values of T and much lower values of C would yield an appropriate tow strength. For instance, $T=220$ and $C=300$ yielded a 5th percentile tow transverse tensile strength of 67 MPa, but a 5th percentile tow shear strength of only 32 MPa. Because of these issues, further investigation was made into the behavior of the fiber-matrix model under shear.

It has been widely observed that composites fail in very different ways under transverse tension and shear. Transverse tensile loading of a composite leads to brittle failure dominated by rupture of the matrix and failure of the interfaces between fibers and matrix. Investigations [21] have shown that the reason for this brittle behavior is the strongly hydrostatic stress-state of the matrix in regions between fibers when transverse tensile loading is applied. Even the most ductile materials, when subjected to purely hydrostatic loads, will fail in a brittle manner. The local stresses that develop in a composite under in-plane shear loading, however, are entirely different.

Under shear loading, composite laminates have been widely observed to undergo highly nonlinear stress-strain behavior. This is because the stresses that develop in the matrix lead to ductile behavior locally. It was observed from the fiber-matrix model that under pure longitudinal shear loading, all local normal stress components in the microstructure were identically zero everywhere, meaning that according to Eq. (5), matrix failure under pure shear will always be ductile in nature. The simple quadrature point deletion approach to degradation does not accurately represent the gradual redistribution of loads that occurs when this ductile failure occurs in the matrix. As a result, this degradation approach

predicts brittle failure of the composite under both transverse tension *and* shear, as shown in Fig. 7.

In order to more accurately represent the behavior observed in composites under shear, the degradation model was modified to gradually decrease material stiffness under ductile failure. This approximates the gradual redistribution of stress around material which is undergoing ductile failure better than quadrature point deletion, albeit at a significant cost in computation time due to a large increase in the number of damage iterations required for each load step. Using this gradual degradation procedure, matrix strengths of $T=128$ MPa and $C=204$ MPa yielded 5th percentile tow strengths within 1 MPa of experimental values. Fig. 8 shows the resulting effective stress-strain behaviors.

These values for matrix strength are far more realistic than those obtained using the quadrature point deletion method. Furthermore, this gradual degradation approach results in nonlinear stress-strain behavior under shear (Fig. 8b). This behavior bears much stronger resemblance to experimentally observed behavior than that seen for quadrature point deletion (Fig. 7b). When using quadrature point deletion, matrix strengths of $T=128$ MPa and $C=204$ MPa result in a 5th percentile tow shear strength of less than 30 MPa. This suggests that under shear loading, the use of a quadrature point deletion scheme causes failure to occur suddenly at a much lower stress level than it would in reality.

Additionally, it was observed that the gradual degradation model did not change the brittle nature of failure under transverse tension (Fig. 8a), indicating that this degradation model is appropriate for both load cases.

5.1.3 Effect of Thermal Loading

Once matrix strengths were determined for the micromechanics model, failure of the tows under transverse tension was examined for four temperatures. This was done using the quad-point deletion approach. The use of gradual quad-point deletion will be the subject of future studies. This and subsequent investigations in this paper focused on the transverse tensile failure of the composite, which appeared to be fairly well behaved for both degradation approaches (in contrast to shear

failure). In these models, only the influence of thermally-induced stress is examined – property dependence of the matrix on temperature is not considered. This study allows the effect of thermal stresses on the tow strength distribution to be characterized. At each temperature, an ensemble of over 200 realizations of 100 fiber RVEs was run and the tow strength distribution was obtained. The stress-free cure temperature was assumed to be 180 °C. Temperatures of 20 °C, 70 °C, 120 °C, and 170 °C were examined. Fig. 9 shows the 5th, 50th, and 95th percentile values from the strength distributions at each of these temperatures.

There was a slight increase in predicted strength going from 20°C to 50°C, after which further temperature increase results in an overall decrease in tow strength. Although the temperature dependence of the strength is moderate, it is interesting to note that the maximum transverse tensile strength is obtained at a temperature well below the stress-free temperature. This suggests that the thermally-induced stresses from cure tend to strengthen the tows to a certain extent. However, it appears that below a certain temperature, further cooling results in weakening of the tows.

5.2 Textile Scale Behavior

Once the tow strength distribution at a given temperature has been determined, that distribution can be utilized within larger scale analyses. As described previously, this was accomplished by seeding the cohesive strength parameters at the quadrature points of the the intra-tow cohesive zones using the tow strength distribution from the fiber-matrix model. A progressive failure analysis was performed on the textile unit cell for a temperature of 170°C. This temperature was selected because it represents a major departure from the temperature at which the fiber-matrix model was calibrated to an experiment. The Weibull distribution for transverse normal strength at this temperature has a shape parameter of 19.68 and a scale parameter of 59.9 MPa. The shear strength distribution has a shape parameter of 6.847 and a scale parameter of 100 MPa. The probability density functions from Eq. (1) for these parameters are shown in Fig. 10.

The textile was subjected to simulated normal loading along the x-direction (Fig. 1). This load was expected to cause failure in the y-direction tows primarily due to transverse tension. This loading will not result in the development of large shear tractions across the cohesive zones, and so any inaccuracy due to incorrect shear strengths should be small.

Four different variations were examined for the textile model with tow strengths randomly seeded from the distributions of Fig. 10. These were compared to models with uniform transverse tow strengths of 60 MPa (the experimentally determined strength for a unidirectional laminate at room temperature) and 51.5 MPa (the 5th percentile tow strength from the fiber-matrix model simulations for 170 °C).

The resulting opening of the intra-tow cohesive zones for these different models is shown in Fig. 11. It was observed that there was very little difference in the extent of cohesive zone opening between the different variations of models with randomly seeded strengths. There are slight differences between the models with randomly seeded strengths and each of the models that have uniform tow strengths. For all models, damage growth typically occurred in fairly distinct stages. As strain was increased, the total area of opened cohesive zones suddenly underwent a large increase over a small strain increment and then subsequently leveled off. Then, at a higher strain, another sudden jump in opened cohesive zone area would occur. As expected, these large jumps in open cohesive zone area tended to happen at lower strain levels for the model with a constant normal cohesive zone strength of 51.5 MPa and higher strain levels for the model with a constant strength of 60 MPa. The major failure events for the models with variable strength tended to lie between the two constant-strength models, indicating that the presence of low-strength regions in the model does not result in large-scale development of damage at lower loads. This may be because failure that starts in low strength regions is arrested once it grows to a higher strength region or because in the four examined realizations, low-strength regions didn't happen to correspond to

high-stress regions of the textile. Further investigation is required to decisively address either possibility.

6 Conclusions

Investigations were performed at both the fiber-matrix microscale and at the textile scale. At the microscale, the investigation into the effect of RVE size on the tow strength distribution showed that larger RVE sizes had less variation in predicted tow strength. Furthermore, the lower end of the tow strength distribution was consistent across all RVE sizes examined. These findings suggest that larger RVE sizes are more likely to contain severe microstructural features that reduce their predicted tow strength. This is informative regarding the issue of matching predicted tow strength distribution to an experimentally observed strength. A unidirectional test specimen is in essence a very large RVE. Therefore, its strength as measured in experiments is most comparable to the lower-end of the tow strength distribution obtained using smaller RVE sizes.

By performing a comparison between experimental observations and predictions from simulation, it was possible to determine strength parameters for the matrix which caused the fiber-matrix model to yield a tow strength matching experimental values. This was accomplished through the solution of an inverse problem. This study indicated a strong sensitivity to the selected degradation approach. A simple quadrature point deletion approach yielded matrix strengths that were unrealistically large, especially the compressive strength. These large matrix strengths were required to obtain appropriate tow strengths under shear. Further investigation showed that this degradation approach did not predict the nonlinear stress-strain response that is typical of composites loaded in shear. As a result, the degradation model was modified to gradually apply degradation to the matrix under stress states that cause ductile failure. This modification was observed to result in much more realistic stress-strain behavior under shear. Furthermore, the matrix strengths obtained using this degradation approach were much more realistic. These findings highlight the importance in accurately representing the

redistribution of stresses that occur due to local ductile failure of the matrix in the composite under shear loading, and indicate that failure to do so leads to premature prediction of transverse tow failure.

Once appropriate matrix strengths were determined, the fiber-matrix model was used to investigate tow strength dependence on thermally-induced stress. It was noted that the maximum tow strength was predicted at a stress between cure temperature and room temperature, indicating that the thermally-induced stress from moderate post-cure cooling tends to reduce the severity of the local stresses associated with transverse tensile loading, delaying failure of the fiber-matrix.

The final investigation was for a textile unit cell model under uniaxial loading. Strengths were assigned to intra-tow cohesive zone quadrature points using the distribution obtained from the fiber-matrix model for a given temperature. Predictions from these variable-strength models were compared to models with uniform transverse tow strengths. For the configuration investigated, there was very little variation in the extent of damage development between different seedings of the strength values. Furthermore, it was observed that the damage behavior of the model with varying strength values fell approximately between the behaviors of models with uniform tow strength values that did and did not account for effect of thermal stresses on tow strength. This suggests that the presence of locally low strength values in the textile does not necessarily lead to the development of tow cracking at lower loads. It remains to be determined whether this is because low-strength regions did not coincide with high-stress regions in the textile or because failure starting in low-strength regions is arrested by adjacent regions with higher strength.

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Fig. 1. Data-flow in multi-scale analysis

Fig. 2. Bilinear traction separation law.

Fig. 4. Cohesive zone elements in Y tow

Fig. 3. Textile mesh

Fig. 5. Probability density of strength for various RVE sizes

(a) Transverse tension

(b) Longitudinal shear

Fig. 6. Distributions yielding appropriate 5th % strengths

(a) Transverse tension

(b) Longitudinal shear

Fig. 7. Stress-strain behavior using quad-point deletion approach. T=239MPa, C=2601 MPa

(a) Transverse tension

(b) Longitudinal shear

Fig. 8. Stress-strain behavior with gradual degradation. T=128 MPa, C=204 MPa

Fig. 9. Transverse tensile tow strength variation (5th, 50th, 95th % values) with temperature

Fig. 11. Cohesive zone opening in y tows for plain weave, T=170°C

Fig. 10. Probability functions of strength distributions used in textile unit-cell analysis

Table 1. Constituent properties for microscale model

IM7 Carbon Fiber		8552 Epoxy	
E_1	276 (GPa)	E	4.67 (GPa)
E_2	22.4 (GPa)	ν	0.35
G_{12}	12.0 (GPa)	α	43.35e-6 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)
G_{23}	7.53 (GPa)		
ν_{12}	0.274		
α_{11}	-4.0e-7 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)		
α_{22}	6.94e-6 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)		

Table 2. Elastic properties of IM7-8552 tow with $\nu_f=60\%$

E_1	167 (GPa)
E_2	11.6 (GPa)
G_{12}	5.23 (GPa)
G_{23}	3.87 (GPa)
ν_{12}	0.3
α_{11}	1.4e-7 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)
α_{22}	2.39e-5 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)

Table 3. Cohesive interface properties

Interface	G_{Ic} (N/m)	G_{IIc} (N/m)	η	τ_n^0 (MPa)	τ_t^0 (MPa)
Inter-tow interface [20]	2.0e2	1.0e3	1.45	60	90
Tow-matrix interface	2.0e2*	1.0e3*	1.45*	60*	90*
Intra-tow crack	20	100	1.45	From fiber-matrix	From fiber-matrix
Intra-matrix crack [22]	6.8e2	1.0e3*	1.45*	120	180*

*Assumed value not provided in literature